

Studies on removal of arsenic in contaminated water by using Assam coal

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Manuscript received 22 April 2010, revised 05 May 2011, accepted 20 June 2011

Abstract : In this study, arsenic removal from arsenic contaminated water has been investigated by using Assam coal as an adsorbent. Arsenic contaminated water was treated in two ways : batch sorption system and continuous flow system through a column. The results show that the low grade Assam coal, collected from Jaipur coalfield, Assam, India, can be used as an effective adsorbent in removing arsenic from water after a simple pretreatment. The optimum conditions for the efficient removal of arsenic are established by observing effective variables such as dose of adsorbent, contact time, and particle size of adsorbent.

Keywords : Adsorption, adsorbent, oxidation, groundwater, arsenic removal.

Introduction

The contamination of arsenic in water can lead to serious health hazards to the population exposed to it. It has been reported that arsenic in drinking water supply affect millions of people worldwide in countries like Bangladesh, India, Taiwan, and Japan¹⁻⁴ etc. Arsenic contamination in ground water of North Eastern Region of India, particularly Assam has been reported by some workers⁵, which indicates the potentiality of posing serious health hazard to the local population of the region. On the other hand, the presence of arsenic, even at high concentration, is not accompanied by any change in taste, odors, and visible appearance of water. Therefore, the presence of arsenic in water is difficult to detect without complex analytical techniques and may pose a significant health hazard unknowingly to the exposed population. The Environmental Protection Agency reduced the Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) for arsenic in drinking water from 50 to 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ due to the international crisis about arsenic contamination and associated health effects on human. According to the recent editions of WHO guidelines for drinking water quality, 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ was established as a provisional guideline value for arsenic⁶.

The chemistry of arsenic includes the existence of different oxidation states. The most common in natural waters being arsenite (AsO_3^{3-}) and arsenate (AsO_4^{3-}), re-

ferred to as arsenic(III) and arsenic(V). Pentavalent species predominates and is stable in oxygen rich aerobic environments. Trivalent arsenites predominate in moderately reducing anaerobic environments such as ground water⁷. So far, a variety of methods such as adsorption⁸, coagulation/precipitation^{9,10}, ion exchange¹¹, membranes¹² have been employed to treat arsenic in water systems. Twindell *et al.*¹³ reported the precipitation of Fe^{III} -arsenate or arsenate co-precipitation with excess iron ($\text{Fe}/\text{As} > 3 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$). It is also reported that granular activated alumina has been applied for the removal of As from water^{14,15}. However, some of these processes are expensive or require the control of pH and or other parameters to achieve the optimum arsenic removal capacity. Therefore, a more effective and economical technique would be highly desirable. Attention has been paid by us to the development of new adsorbent from natural raw material such as Assam coal which is low cost, locally available and nontoxic. The North Eastern Region of India, particularly Assam is endowed with considerable deposit of coal, which has been estimated to be about 900 million tons. The problem of using these coals both in domestic and industrial purposes are mainly due to their high sulphur content, friability and low ash fusion range. Their physical and chemical constitution is so ambiguous that they can not be categorized under a definite rank. Their caking index and oxygen put them into

the category of high rank bituminous coal, whereas considering their carbon and sulphur content, and friability they may be classified as low rank coals. Because of such high sulphur content, the coals of this region pose problem for its commercial exploitation. Therefore, more attention is being paid by the researchers for indirect utilization of these coals. The present study aims at using low grade Assam coal for removal of arsenic from arsenic contaminated water of North East Region. The new adsorbent is locally available, low cost and nontoxic adsorbent. To render it safe for use in drinking water, a pre-treatment procedure was adopted. This pretreated adsorbent could be used successfully for removal of arsenic from contaminated water.

Experimental

All chemicals used in this study were analytical grade and all stock solutions were prepared with double distilled water from an Ultra Quartz Double Distillation system. The adsorbent, low grade Assam coal, was collected from Jaipur coalfield, Assam, India. The coal sample was ground to five different particle sizes for the present study such as 180, 255, 450, 900 and 1600 μm . The characteristics of the coal samples were evaluated by IS method (IS : 1350, 2000) and are included in Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of water samples were evaluated by IS method (IS : 10500, 1991) and are included in Table 2. The arsenic concentrations in the water samples, before and after experiment were determined with an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Model : A Analyst-700).

Table 1. Composition of adsorbent before and after pretreatment

Sl. no.	Parameters	% Composition	
		Before treatment	After treatment
1.	Moisture	4.3	4.4
2.	Ash	8.5	8.4
3.	Volatile matter	42.7	42.6
4.	Fixed carbon	14.5	44.6
5.	Carbon	68.1	68.0
6.	Hydrogen	5.9	5.8
7.	Nitrogen	1.3	1.0
8.	Sulfur	2.8	2.3
9.	Oxygen	21.9	22.9
10.	C.V.	6830 kcal/kg	6830 kcal/kg

Table 2. Physico-chemical properties of water sample before and after treatment

Parameters	Raw water	Treated water
pH	6.8	6.8
Turbidity (NTU)	1.4	1.2
Hardness (as CaCO_3)	130	128
Calcium (as CaCO_3)	83	82
Magnesium (as CaCO_3)	46	45
Dissolved iron as Fe	0.2	0.18
Sulphate	1.9	1.4
Chloride	1.5	0.8
Nitrate	0.5	0.4
Methyl orange alkalinity	118	115
Arsenic	0.130	0.01
Total dissolved solid	129	125

*All parameters are in mg/L, excepting pH and NTU.

Pre-treatment of adsorbent :

Since low grade Assam coals are high in sulfur content, it has inherent disadvantage of releasing soluble sulfur compounds in contact with water, thereby, lowering the pH value of water to an acidic range. Therefore, to maintain the normal pH in treated water (6.5 to 8.5), it is desirable to remove the water soluble sulphur compounds from the low grade Assam coal before it can be used as an adsorbent for removal of arsenic from water. For the pretreatment, the coal samples were washed and boiled with distilled water containing 1% ferric alum for one hour. The material after rinsing with distilled water and filtering was dried in hot air oven at 50 °C for one hour. Though this removal can be achieved by treating with boiling water, it has been found advantageous to use 1% ferric alum. The addition of ferric alum not only helps in removing the undesirable components from low grade coal but also enhance its adsorption characteristics.

Pre-oxidation of arsenites to arsenates :

A significant problem is encountered in the removal of arsenic in water i.e. the arsenites and arsenates both have been found to be present simultaneously in many contaminated natural water¹⁶. Arsenic(III) compounds are primarily nonionic whereas arsenic(V) compounds are ionic at normal drinking water pH¹⁷. Arsenic(III) compounds or arsenites are, therefore, not always readily removed from drinking water by methods that are very effective for removal of arsenic(V) compounds or arsenates. It is,

therefore, necessary to pre-oxidize any arsenites present to arsenates in order to effectively remove arsenic from drinking water to safe levels. Therefore, water samples were treated with KMnO_4 (~1 ppm) before treatment with the adsorbent in order to oxidize As^{III} to As^{V} . The oxidation agent KMnO_4 is a safe solution that can be manually or automatically metered and it does not interfere with the adsorbent or the treatment system.

Batch sorption experiment :

Batch sorption experiments were carried out for the water samples. About 0.1–2.0 g of the adsorbent was introduced into a plastic vial containing 100 ml of arsenic contaminated water sample. The particle size of the adsorbent used was 255 μm . The mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer for about 2 h at room temperature. At the end of the desired contact time, the plastic vials were removed from the stirrer and allowed to stand for 2 min for settling the adsorbent. The water samples were filtered using sintered crucible (G-4) and filtrate was analyzed for residual arsenic. Experiments were conducted to determine the optimum adsorbent dose, particle size of adsorbent and contact time of the adsorbent with the water samples.

Column experiment :

To evaluate the arsenic-sorbing performance of the adsorbent in a flow-through system, column experiments were carried out. The experimental device consisted of opaque PVC open ended column with 50 cm height and 5 cm diameter. The treated adsorbent was packed to the height of 40 cm of the column. The water samples were allowed to pass through under gravity flow and the eluent were collected for determination of arsenic content.

Results and discussion

Effect of adsorbent dosage in batch sorption experiment :

The residual arsenic in the water samples containing 130 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of initial arsenic concentrations decreased with increase of dose of adsorbent. The optimum dose of adsorbent was found to be 1.5 g/100 ml where 92.5 percent removal of arsenic was achieved and arsenic level found in the treated water was 9.8 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Effect of contact time in batch sorption experiment :

The percentage removal of arsenic by the new adsor-

bent was studied for different contact times by treating with optimum dose (1.5 g/100 ml) of adsorbent having particle size of 255 μm for As contaminated water having concentration 130 $\mu\text{g/L}$. As contact time was increased, percentage removal of arsenic also initially increased, but gradually approached to an almost constant value at about 120 min.

Effect of particle size in batch sorption experiment :

The effect of particle size of the adsorbent on adsorption of arsenic from water was also studied. The experiments were conducted separately by using various particle sizes of the adsorbent (1600 μm to 180 μm). It was found that the particle size plays a very important role in the adsorption of arsenic and its removal. The optimum particle size was found to be 255 μm . Further reduction of particle size was found to interfere with subsequent filtration. Particle sizes 450 μm and above was found to be non effective in arsenic removal.

Effect of variables in column experiment :

In column experiment, the flow time was found inversely proportional to arsenic removal capacity. An optimum flow of 10 ml/min was found to remove 85% arsenic in a single flow experiment using 255 μm size particles. Recirculation of the eluent was found to follow an exponential character in arsenic removal under above flow condition. Particle size played an equally important role in flow experiment as in the case of batch experiment. With higher particle size arsenic removal was insignificant. Lower particle size than 255 μm was unsuitable for column material.

Adsorption kinetics :

The rate constant k_{ad} for adsorption of arsenic, for the adsorbent was studied by applying Lagergren rate equation :

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - k_{\text{ad}} \frac{t}{2.303} \quad (1)$$

where q_e and q (both in mg/g) are the amounts of arsenic adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t , respectively. Straight line plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ versus t at different times indicate the validity of Lagergren rate equation (Fig. 1). The value of k_{ad} at room temperature (25 °C) was calculated from the slope of the plot and was found to be 2.87×10^{-2} . As in Fig. 1, linearity of the plot indicates the

Fig. 1

applicability of the first-order kinetics equation for the system under experimental conditions.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) studies :

Adsorption reaction may lead to changes in molecular and crystalline structure of the adsorbent and hence an understanding of the molecular and crystalline structures of the adsorbent and the resulting changes thereof would provide valuable information regarding adsorption reaction. Hence, XRD patterns of the adsorbent before and after treatment with contaminated water have been studied. The XRD patterns of the adsorbent before and after treatment are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The adsorbent sample was porous in nature. It is evident that the XRD

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of the adsorbent before adsorption.

pattern of the adsorbent after treatment with contaminated water, exhibits no variation in the structure and this suggest that arsenic(v) ions might diffuse into micro pores and macro pores and adsorb mostly by physisorption without altering the structure of the adsorbent.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of the adsorbent after desorption.

Conclusions :

In this study, it has been demonstrated that the treated low grade Assam coal of specific particle size is an effective adsorbent for removal of arsenic from drinking water. There is no adverse change in the physico-chemical properties of treated water. Pretreatment of the coal is simple and cost effective.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. P. G. Rao, Director, North East Institute of Science and Technology, Jorhat, Assam, India for inspiration and permission to publish this paper.

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